

Appendix A: Stack excluding quiescent galaxies

As shown on Figure 2 the sample is biased toward sources below the main sequence. To make sure that quiescent galaxies do not bias our analysis and the derived average dust masses, we repeat our stacking analysis after removing all sources with $\Delta MS < -0.5$. In total, 2157 galaxies are removed from the sample, leading to a final size of 1946 after removing quiescent galaxies. The results are shown on Figures A.1 and A.2.

Fig. A.1. Similar to Figure 4 but all sources with $\Delta MS < -0.5$ are excluded. Error bars are computed in the same way as on Figure 4.

Fig. A.2. Similar to Figure A.1 but for SFR instead of stellar mass.

The main difference appear on the stellar mass subsamples, where the derived dust masses are overall higher –especially in the high-stellar mass regime– after excluding quiescent galaxies (although some bins appear now undetected, likely due to the lower number of sources stacked). This suggest that quiescent galaxies may be overall more dust-poor at given stellar mass, driving the average down when included in the entire sample. In any event, the overall trends observed in the main analysis seem to be confirmed even when removing sources with $\Delta MS < -0.5$. One can note that our dust mass measurements are also in better agreement with previous individual results when quiescent galaxies are excluded from the stacks.

Appendix B: Fit results

On Figures B.1 and B.2 are shown the average dust mass recovered as function of stellar mass, SFR or redshift, superposed with the corresponding fit. Only the detections (i.e. S/N above 3σ , see Section 3) are shown and used in the fit. The coefficients of the fits are shown on Table 5.

Fig. B.1. Similar to Figure 4 the corresponding fits are also plotted. Only detections (S/N above 3σ) are shown on the plot, and fits are only computed for subsamples with three or more data points (similarly for stellar mass subsample, right panel). Fits are plotted with a continuous (dashed) line when within (outside) the data points range.

Fig. B.2. Similar to Figure B.1 but for SFR instead of stellar mass.

Appendix C: Distribution of SFR and stellar mass in the subsamples

On Figures C.1 and C.2 are shown the distribution of stellar mass and SFR in the different subsamples. The mean and median values for each subsamples are also shown as red and black vertical lines respectively.

Fig. C.1. Distribution of the (log) stellar mass of galaxies in each subsamples. The red (black) vertical line indicates the mean (median) stellar mass of the subsample.

Fig. C.2. Similar to Figure B.1 but for SFR instead of stellar mass.

Appendix D: Bootstrapping results

On Figures D.1 and D.2 we show the distribution of the results from our bootstrapping analyses. For each subsample, 1000 new subsamples are randomly selected (see Jolly et al. 2020, for a detailed description of the bootstrapping tool included in LINESTACKER and used here), and their stack values are collected. The distribution of these stack results (normalized to the original stack result of the corresponding subsample) are shown. Color coding is used to distinguish between the detected (in cyan) and not detected (in red) subsamples. A vertical line is placed at $x = 1$ to guide the eye.

Fig. D.1. Distribution of the bootstrap stack results, normalized by the dust mass of the original stack. Black vertical lines at $x=1$ indicate the expected location of the peak distribution. Histograms in cyan (red) represents the subsample for which the signal was higher (lower) than 3σ .

Fig. D.2. Similar to Figure D.1 but for the SFR subsamples. The 3 subsamples containing only 1 source were excluded from this analysis.

Appendix E: Dust mass inferred from median stacking

In addition to the mean stacking analyses we performed median stacking for each of the subsamples, in the same way as described in the main analysis. The median stacking stamps are shown on Figure 8 and here we show the dust mass evolution as a function of stellar mass and redshift (Figure E.1) and as a function of SFR and redshift (Figure E.2), similar to Figures 4 and 6. While the median stacking analyses show typically lower dust masses (indicating possible skewed distributions) the results and trends are overall very consistent with the mean stacking analyses.

Fig. E.1. Similar to Figure 4 but using median stacking.

Fig. E.2. Similar to Figure E.1 but for SFR instead of stellar mass.